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Thin silica-based microsheets with controlled geometry

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Abstract:

A high demand for materials with defined geometry and size is required in a wide range of fields. Inorganic compounds, especially silica-based, arise as a cheap source and chemically flexible for the purpose. Silica display unique properties, like easy functionalization and good optical features making an interesting material to manipulate. In this work, we developed a method to create thin silica microsheets with defined size and high-fidelity shape using superhydrophobic-hydrophilic microarrays. These microstructures were produced through sol-gel process using biomimetic superhydrophobic surfaces decorated with wettable spots. The results confirm the manufacture of porous silica microstructures with defined design (squares and circles) and thickness around 7 μm . The methodology applied in this work enables the high throughput fabrication of shaped silica materials in a single step, unlocking an extensive number of applications in areas that require miniaturization, like microelectronics or in fields like sensing and biomedicine.

In the last decade, researchers have witnessed an increased use of inorganic materials, especially silica-based, to develop new solutions in a wide range of different areas from electronics,^[1,2] environmental,^[3] to biomedical and pharmaceutical.^[4–7] Silica has become a very attractive compound due to its properties such as inertness, easy functionalization, simple processability and mechanical robustness.^[8,9] This compound can be found, in nature, in both crystalline and amorphous forms.

Despite the numerous methods reported in literature like sublimation^[10], microemulsion^[11], vapor-phase synthesis^[12] to produce silica-based materials, sol-gel process has been highlighted due to the simplicity of the method as well as the ability to control and produce different configurations (fibers, films, nanoparticles).^[13–16] Such process is not only applied to the synthesis of inorganic materials but also in the manufacture of inorganic-organic hybrids.^[17,18] Furthermore, this process can occur at mild conditions, which enables its use with biological compounds that are more prone to harsh conditions.^[19,20]

The control over different reaction conditions such as pH and hydrolysis/condensation kinetics can influence distinct features of the resulting materials such as porosity, size and shape.^[21,22]

Concerning to parameters like defined shape and size, the production of two dimensional (2D) microstructures/nanostructures of silica are poorly described, and in most cases, they are reported as hybrid materials produced under complex protocols.^[23,24]

Looking from a biological perspective, miniaturization is an area of high interest to be explored due to the potential of developing new solutions for sensing and diagnostic applications.^[25] In this context, microarray platforms established by Levkin and collaborators allow the design of systems that enable the production of materials with a specific and high-fidelity geometry and size. These microarrays have been used for the production of microgels, cell screening and other applications.^[26,27] The technology underlying these bioinspired platforms is based on the different wettability characters, namely, superhydrophobic-hydrophilic^[28,29]. They are characterized by displaying zones with different characters, namely, a superhydrophobic one that repels aqueous solutions and possesses water contact angles (WCAs) greater than 150° and a superhydrophilic that allows the deposition of water droplets and shows WCAs less than 10°. Neto *et al.* have reported the use of these platforms for the production of hydrogel particles, achieving a high throughput production by using the discontinuous dewetting effect.^[27] Such event allows a spontaneous separation of an aqueous solution into microdroplets without complex methods. Recently, these platforms have been engineered to manufacture microstructures using inorganic-organic materials. Tsotsalas *et al.* successfully produced free standing microstructures of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) with possible applications in the fields of catalysis, sensing or biomedicine^[30] In this work, pure silica-based microsheets were created for the first time, using these microarrays with specific geometry.

We produced superhydrophobic-hydrophilic platforms based on the procedure described elsewhere.^[26] Briefly, on a microscope glass slide was formed a nanoporous film of poly(2-hydroxyethylmethacrylate-co-ethylene dimethacrylate) followed by a modification of the polymer surface with alkyne groups via esterification. The specific geometry pattern was formed by functionalizing the surface with 1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorodecanethiol through a thiol-yne photo-click reaction by using the application of corresponding quartz photomask. The remaining alkyne groups were reacted with 2-mercaptoethanol

under UV light to form the desired pattern of highly hydrophilic areas surrounded by superhydrophobic borders.

Figure 1 – Schematic representation of the protocol to produce silica-based microstructures of defined geometries.

Any geometry and size can be accomplished since the liquid solution is confined inside the hydrophilic areas and the design is determined by the quartz photomask. The geometry adopted within this work were circles and squares with the following sizes: squares with an edge of 1020 μm and circles with a diameter of 1015 μm . A schematic protocol of the production of silica-based microstructures can be seen in Figure 1.

After the production of the microarrays with the desire patterning, the next step was to produce the silica microstructures. To enable silica deposition and, at the same time, avoid the reaction with microscope glass slide, a sacrificial layer composed of gelatin was applied first. Gelatin is a biopolymer and was chosen as a sacrificial material due to its thermoresponsive properties and the ability to maintain the micropatterning geometry. To do so, a 10% (w/v) gelatin solution was applied to the microarrays forming a rigid droplet confined in the microarray. Then, to increase the hardness of the support layer, the microscope glass slide containing the gelatin droplets was incubated at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 minutes. Different precursors can be used to promote the synthesis where the most used and well described in the literature are silicon alkoxides, specifically, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS)

and tetramethyl orthosilicate (TMOS).^[31–33] The formation of silica using the sol-gel process was optimized for this procedure. Firstly, 500 μL of TMOS was used as silica source and the reaction of hydrolysis was conducted under acidic pH by adding 100 μL of 100 mM of hydrochloric acid (HCl) and 20 μL of distilled water (dH_2O) under magnetic stirring.

Particular in this experiment, the use of acidic medium promoted a slower hydrolysis which in consequence lead to the formation of more linear molecules with cross-linking that can branch.^[34] This type of reaction slowly thickens the solution and finally becomes a gel. The slow thickening of the solution allowed the droplet of sol-gel solution to be deposited into the gelatin and stay within the microarray geometry without drain to hydrophobic border.^[35] After the solution started to thicken, which occurs after 48 hours, the silica acid solution was applied in each gelatin microarray. Immediately after, the glass slide was kept in an oven to dry the wet gel for 5 minutes at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Then, to release silica microstructures from the arrays, the microscope glass slides were put in a water bath at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ until they start to detach. The resulting microstructures were easily collected to be further characterized through different techniques.

Such free standing behavior is due to the low surface energy of the sacrificial gelatin layer which decreases for higher concentrations of gelatin as previously reported.^[36] Gelatin's thermoresponsive properties and adsorption/desorption behavior was also inspected by quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D). After the adsorption of the gelatin film onto the Au-plated quartz crystal resonator at room temperature, its desorption was observed while raising the temperature to 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (See Supporting Information), thus corroborating the aforementioned findings.

First, size and shape fidelity were analyzed and confirmed through optical microscopy. The diameter of circles and the square edge were measured as well as their thickness. Considering that the edge of square of the microarray is 1020 μm , the squares edges of the obtained microstructures have a range between 300-400 μm , with media value of 354 $\mu\text{m} \pm 62$. Similarly, considering that the diameter of circular pattern is 1015 μm , the diameters obtained for circle-shaped structures also varies between 300-400 μm with a media value of 339 $\mu\text{m} \pm 29$. Based on these results, we concluded that shrinkage of size was observed in both shapes. This phenomenon can be explained by the evaporation of solvents like water, methanol and other volatile components during the drying of the silica-based microsheets. Such event had already been described in literature for other silica structures. In the drying process, the amount of shrinkage is dependent on the stiffness of the network.^[17,37] In our case, such contraction did not compromise the final geometry of the final silica objects. Microsheets' cross section allowed the measurement of the thickness which is approximately 7 μm (Figure 2E). Moreover, when compared to a previous work where polymeric microgels have been fabricated with a thickness of around 13 μm ,^[27] our values are in agreement.

Figure 2 – Characterization of the silica microsheets. A and B – SEM and EDS of a silicon (Si) square shaped microstructure respectively; C and D – SEM and EDS of a circle shaped microstructure; E – Cross-section of the microsheets with the measured thickness; F and G – FTIR and XRD characterization of the microstructures.

To further characterize the silica morphology and identify the chemical composition of these microstructures, scanning electronic microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analysis were performed. SEM/EDS results confirmed that these microstructures are composed of silicon through elementary map of these structures which also shows a black area (Figure 2B and D). This region can be explained as the shaped microsheets are not totally flat and gain a shell-like deformation due the droplet-shape acquired by the gelatin during its deposition on the microarray.

Furthermore, the cross section of the shaped microsheets display an interconnected porous network, as shown in Figure 2E.

When we compare the formation of these microstructures to that of silica thin films production, we could observe a similar behavior that could explain the porous morphology. In this context, a competition of two processes might be occurring: the evaporation, which tends to shrink the structure, and the condensation that continues to occur after the deposition and tends to stiffen the structure which delays the shrinking phenomenon.^[38] The silica acid solution is already viscous when applied so the network must be supporting the compaction caused by the rapid evaporation and allowing the formation of the porosity. As previously explained, the conditions of pH, silica source, drying process of sol-gel technique could affect the outcome.

To chemically characterize the produced silica-based microstructures, Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis were performed. Figure 2F displays the FTIR spectrum of microstructures with typical peaks and bands displayed by silica. A large band in the region between 900 – 1200 cm^{-1} is normally attributed to a combination of vibrations resulting of the silica network, specifically the peak at 1090 cm^{-1} that can be attributed to the stretching vibrations of Si-O-Si and the 937 cm^{-1} attributed to stretching vibrations of the free silanol group on surface of silica network.^[39,40] The XRD analysis of the silica microstructures showed the lack of crystallinity in the sample confirming the amorphous nature of the shaped microstructures herein produced (Figure 2G).

In summary, a novel and simple method for producing free-standing thin silica microstructures with well-defined geometry was reported. This enabling technology has a widespread potential not only due to silica properties but also due to the simplicity of processing. In fact, in one simple step a high quantity of silica microstructures with a defined design can be produced which can have an important impact in high throughput processes with multiple experiments for areas like sensing or diagnostics. The possibility to control the sol-gel reaction allows the manufacture of other type of geometries or even use of other type of inorganic materials and hybrid systems. We speculated that

future studies would allow to produce microparticles with more controlled ultrastructure, including mesopores with fixed geometries and sizes, and surface post-functionalization, that could find new applications in microelectronics, photonics, environmental, catalysis, or in bottom-up tissue engineering applications.^[41]

Experimental section:

Microarrays production: 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA) and ethylene dimethacrylate (EDMA) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and purified using a short column filled with basic aluminium oxide to eliminate the inhibitors. 3-(trimethoxysilyl) propyl methacrylate, 2,2-dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone, 1-decanol, 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine, perfluorodecanethiol, trichloro(1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyl)silane, cyclohexanol were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Pentynoic acid, N,N'-diisopropylcarbodiimide and 2-mercaptoethanol were purchased from ThermoFischer Scientific and dichloromethane from VWR. All the chemicals were used as received. The superhydrophobic-hydrophilic microarrays were prepared according to the protocol described by Feng and colleagues.^[26]

Silica microstructures formation: Gelatin from porcine skin (gel strength 300 g Bloom), tetramethylorthosilicate (TMOS) and hydrochloric acid 37% (HCl) were purchased by Sigma Aldrich and used as received. Gelatin was dissolved in Milli-Q water at 60 °C.

Optical microscopy: Optical microscope images were acquired using Zeiss Microscope Primovert. *ImageJ* software was used to measure the microstructures edge size.

SEM/EDS: Silica microstructures were previously dried at 37 °C and coated with a thin layer of evaporated carbon. Morphological and compositional images were acquired out by SEM (accelerating voltage 15 kV, SEM Hitachi, SU-70 instrument) coupled with an EDS (Bruker, Quantax 400 detector) with exposure time of 300 s.

FTIR: The microstructures were previously crushed and mixed with potassium bromide (KBr) purchased from Sigma Aldrich to form a pellet. The measurements were performed in a range between 4000 and 500 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and averaging 120 scans, at room temperature, using a Mattson 7000 spectrometer.

XRD: XRD data were measured using a Panalytical Emperean diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) in $\theta - 2\theta$ geometry with a linear detector and fixed divergence slit.

QCM-D: The build-up of the gelatin film was monitored *in situ* by quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (Q-Sense Pro, Biolin Scientific, Sweden) in a liquid environment. This apparatus measures in real time the frequency and dissipation changes (Δf and ΔD , respectively) of the quartz crystal generated by the adsorption of materials onto the gold-coated 5 MHz AT-cut quartz crystal sensors (AWS SNS 000043 A, Advanced Wave Sensors, Spain). Prior to the QCM-D experiments, the crystals were thoroughly cleaned by immersion into an oxidizing cleaning solution encompassing a 1:1:5 (v/v) mixture of ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH, 25%), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30%), and ultrapure water in an ultrasonic bath at 70 °C for 10 min. Then, the quartz crystal sensors were taken off from this solution, thoroughly rinsed with ultrapure at room temperature water, dried under a soft stream of N₂, and submitted to UV/Ozone (UV/Ozone ProCleaner 220, BioForce Nanosciences, Inc.) treatment for 10 min. The freshly cleaned Au-plated quartz crystal sensors were immediately inserted in the QCM-D apparatus and equilibrated in ultrapure water until a baseline was reached. Then, a 1 mg.mL⁻¹ gelatin aqueous solution was pumped into the QCM-D chamber for 25 min, following by raising the temperature to 60 °C to assess the gelatin's possible desorption owing to its thermoresponsive properties. The gold-coated quartz crystal substrates were excited at multiple overtones (1, 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11, corresponding to 5, 15, 25, 35, 45, and 55 MHz, respectively) and variations in the frequency (Δf) and in

dissipation (ΔD) were monitored in real time. The frequency of each overtone was normalized to the fundamental resonant frequency of the quartz crystal sensor ($\Delta f_n/n$, in which n denotes the overtone number). The results presented in the graphic correspond to the frequency and energy dissipation shifts at the 7th overtone (35 MHz), as they presented the lowest level of noise. However, the data obtained at the 7th overtone are representative of the other overtones. All experiments were performed at a constant flow rate of 50 $\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

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A novel and simple technology for producing silica microsheets with a defined geometry was developed using superhydrophobic-hydrophilic microarrays. A sol-gel process was used to produce silica microsheets with a high-fidelity microstructure.